

THE IMPACT OF CORRUPTION ON THE ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract

According to the statements in the paper, the impact of corruption through its various forms on the environment is presented. Namely, the explanation of these criminalistic, criminal law, environmental, victimological, sociological, health, economic, and many other problems, is increasingly being talked about and written about worldwide because it is gaining momentum. The paper presents an overview of the problem of corruption in the environment, primarily through the processing of: introduction, legislative and legal framework, definition of the term corruption, types of corrupt behaviour, phenomenology of the occurrence of corruption in the environment, consequences of the impacts of corruption on the environment, prevention of future criminal activities, conclusion and used literature. To clarify the impact, several general research methods have been used and through the presentation of recent and older events that are directly related to this type of crime, an attempt has been made to present the phenomenological characteristics of the forms of manifestation encountered, the causal connections between the crime and the perpetrator versus the state response, as well as the failure to take the appropriate legally prescribed measures and activities of state institutions. To achieve the goal, explaining the impact of corruption on the environment, i.e. on persons with public functions and authorities who, through all their influences, obstruct justice and with their corrupt behaviour directly harm the environment, we use the following general research methods: comparative method, statistical method, descriptive method, causal method, method of document content analysis. All these activities have been carried out in a way that makes the illegal activities committed by employees in the environmental sector and other state institutions more accessible, more transparent, and collected in one place, as well as highlighting the inappropriate and irresponsible attitude – and, for unclear reasons, the impunity – of the judicial authorities, and the impact of this complex of illegal activities on the environment. At the same time, we also offer possible ways out of this situation and, above all, through prevention and then repression of corrupt activities in the environment and especially the negative impact of the same. However, we must emphasize that the small number of committed crimes indicates the existence of a huge dark figure.

Keywords: *corruption, environment, prevention, protection*

INTRODUCTION

Environmental pollution has emerged as one of the fastest-growing forms of organized crime globally, causing incalculable harm to ecosystems and, by extension, to humanity. The growth of such crimes often relies on organized networks, institutional protection, and impunity for perpetrators. To understand this phenomenon, it is essential to define key terms:

- **Environment:** the space containing all living organisms and natural resources, including natural and human-created values, their mutual relationships, and the total space in which humans live, including settlements, industrial facilities, and media (SSO, 2024).
- **Environment (alternative definition):** refers to physical and biological systems and their interconnections, distinct from political, economic, and social systems, including their feedback influence on human life (Bajagić, 2007).

To analyse the impact of corruption on the environment, this paper employs general research methods, including comparative, statistical, descriptive, causal, and document content analysis (Mojanoski, 2012).

1. LEGAL AND INSTITUTIONAL FRAMEWORK

Environmental crimes are codified as punishable offences in domestic legislation, including North Macedonia. However, despite legal provisions, institutional responses remain inefficient due to insufficient human resources, inadequate equipment, and corruption (Malish Sazdovska, 2014; Fetaj, 2021). Corruption, often described as a “disease of leaders”, occurs when public officials prioritize private interests over public duties (Mrvić-Petrović & Ćirić, 2004). Legislative instability, frequent amendments, and loopholes create opportunities for tailored laws favoring elites (Taseva, 2021).

These are exactly the cases with the SCPC and their president, as well as the decision of no confidence in members of the Republic Judicial Council, which, due to the adjusted and adapted laws, have no effect on the holders of functions. Here, we are primarily talking about ambiguities, legal loopholes and of course adapting or adjusting the criminal code to the needs of an elite. Regarding this phenomenon, we present the statement of the former President of the Republic of North Macedonia, Stevo Pendarovski, given on TV Telma, on October 15, 2020, **“The biggest problem in our country is high corruption. In all these years, there has been no conviction for a high-ranking official or other person involved in high corruption. Those in power always look to the past and do not pay attention to what is happening today. But even in those cases, there was no effective verdict or the sentences imposed were too low”** (Taseva 2021, 19). Macedonian criminal legislation defines 24 offences addressing corruption (Arnaudovski et al., 2007).

Such a range of criminal acts that prosecute corruption in state bodies necessitated the establishment of a special state body, the **State Commission for the Prevention of Corruption (SCPC)** is tasked with monitoring, prevention, and enforcement (Law on the Prevention of Corruption, Art. 49).

1.1 Systemic Corruption Risks in Environmental Governance

Environmental governance in North Macedonia exhibits structural vulnerabilities that enable corruption at all stages: strategic planning, environmental impact assessment (EIA), permitting, and enforcement (Florozon, 2023a).

High-risk stages include:

- Strategic documents: Susceptible to political and economic influence.
- EIA process: Lack of transparency and selective reporting of expert assessments.
- Permitting: Discretionary authority allows bribery and manipulation.
- Inspection and enforcement: Limited staffing, political interference, and weak reporting undermine compliance (Florozon, 2023a; 2023b).

Together, these risks form an interconnected system of vulnerabilities that facilitate corrupt behaviour in environmental governance.

2. ANTI-CORRUPTION RISKS IN THE ENVIRONMENTAL LEGISLATIVE FRAMEWORK

Recent analyses by the State Commission for the Prevention of Corruption (DKSK, 2021) identify significant corruption-exposure points within the Law on Environment and its associated bylaws. These insights deepen the understanding of how structural vulnerabilities in the legal system facilitate corrupt behaviour related to environmental governance.

2.1 Legal instability

The Law on Environment has undergone 23 amendments, averaging one modification every seven months. Frequent amendments to the Law on Environment create opportunities for selective application and regulatory capture.

2.2 Institutional fragmentation

SCPC notes serious inconsistencies in the distribution of institutional responsibilities. For example, Article 22 requires multiple ministries to jointly issue key environmental protection acts, meaning that the objection or inaction of a single actor can freeze an entire procedure. The Law does not prescribe deadlines for inter-institutional consultation, leaving procedural gaps that can be exploited for corrupt purposes.

2.3 Transparency and public participation gaps

Provisions governing public access to environmental information—such as Article 58 and several accompanying rulebooks (2006–2007)—are outdated and inconsistent with modern transparency standards. SCPC further identifies:

- absence of clear criteria for identifying interested public;
- lack of cross-border public consultation mechanisms for Environmental Impact Assessments (EIAs);
- duplication and contradiction with the Law on Free Access to Public Information.

These defects obstruct civil oversight and create space for non-transparent decision-making.

2.4 Environmental permitting as a high-risk process

A and B Integrated Environmental Permits (Arts. 95–129) are especially vulnerable to corruption. Municipalities are bound by a 30-day deadline, yet no corresponding obligations apply to the Ministry, generating exploitable procedural asymmetries. Rulebooks regulating permitting procedures (2006, 2014, 2016) contain unclear definitions of responsibilities and do not establish minimum standards for public hearings or expert participation.

2.5 Ministerial discretion and weak oversight

The SCPC report highlights the absence of standardized criteria for appointing environmental inspectors, committee members, and agency directors. This discretionary framework allows political influence, undermines accountability, and increases systemic exposure to corruption. Outdated inspection regulations further weaken institutional control mechanisms.

2.6 Alignment with EU acquis

As part of EU accession obligations under Chapter 27, the SCPC emphasizes the need to harmonize strategic environmental assessment (SEA), environmental impact assessment (EIA), and Best Available Techniques (BAT) methodologies. Gaps in SEA, EIA, and BAT implementation undermine transparency and regulatory effectiveness (Florozone, 2023a; 2023b).

3. DEFINING CORRUPTION

As in many other scientific and social fields, there is disagreement in the conceptual definition of corruption. It is very interesting that with the adoption of the first Law on the Prevention of Corruption (Official Gazette No.28/2002), the general concept of corruption was not defined, for which the entire law was composed, but rather two whole years were waited, when with the Law on Amendments and Supplements to the Law on the Prevention of Corruption (Official Gazette No.46/2004) in Article 2, the amendment of Article 1 with Article 1-a was made, which defines corruption as: *"using one's function, public authority, official duty and position to achieve any benefit for oneself or another"*.

According to another author, *"Corruption is the abuse of official position and authority, which is based on the unlawful acquisition of material or other benefits, represented in a narrow sense, and in a broader sense – the provision and use of services, privileges, benefits, as well as bribery, i.e. abuse of office or in another way"* (Miletic, 2001).

Corruption – (lat. corruption – corruption, bribery), in a general sense, neglect and abuse of official authority for personal gain, bribery, bribing of officials. In a broader sense – all forms of abuse of official authority and position through greed (bribery, abuse of position and authority, giving and using privileges, kickbacks, receiving commissions and gifts) and in a narrower sense, the crime of giving and receiving bribes (Aleksić et al. 2004, 134).

Corruption – is the abuse of one's own or someone else's position or function for the purpose of making a profit, obtaining an advantage or gain for oneself or others (Arnaudovski et al. 2007).

According to the *Civil Convention on the Prevention of Corruption*, *"corruption" means: the solicitation, offering or acceptance, directly or indirectly, of an unlawful act or of another undue advantage or promise of such an undue advantage which interferes with the normal performance of a function or prescribed conduct of the beneficiary of the unlawful act, or of the undue advantage or promise of such an advantage* (Official Gazette No.13/2002, Article 2, p.289).

On the other hand, there are authors who define the term corruption differently: *"corruption does not describe or include putting one's fingers in the coffers, but rather treats the abuse of function, position, authorization or disabling of the process of objectively making and implementing decisions and solutions"* (Tsigaridov, 2002, 169).

"Corruption and corrupt behaviour represent a cancer - a wound and a strong blow to the normal systemic state-legal and democratic functioning of the state apparatus. As a criminal phenomenon, it has a constant tendency to spread and create incompatibility with the state-legal structure, its belittling and devaluation, and the consequences are a direct blow to moral and ethical values and the trust of citizens in the institutions of the system" (Milkovski, 2002, 184).

Certain politicians have commented on corruption in certain public appearances, each in their own way, according to the former US president *"Corruption is a cancer: a*

cancer that feeds on citizen trust in democracy, a cancer that weakens the human instinct for innovation and creativity, Joe Biden” (Arifi, 2021).

The EU Ambassador to Macedonia, Rojas, commenting on the individuals involved in politics and the judiciary in high-level corruption, says: *“I think that the Public Prosecutor’s Office should always have the opportunity, in an independent judicial system, to conduct all investigations in the event that there are allegations of possible corruption in an institution, and for this, all mechanisms should be made available to it, all in order to be able to conduct an investigation into allegations of possible corruption” (SAKAMDAKAZAM.MK. 2024).*

4. TYPES OF CORRUPTIVE BEHAVIOUR

According to the majority of authors consulted, several types of corrupt behaviour are evident, which are divided according to where they appear, and are presented as follows:

- **corruption at the lowest level (street);**
- **medium-level corruption in the economic sphere (business);**
- **corruption at the highest level (top), so-called political corruption (Фетаи, 2021)**

We find an additional division in the following forms of corruption:

- **Black** - is the corruption for which the competent courts have rendered a verdict at all levels of the previous division;
- **Gray corruption** – are those corrupt behaviours that relate to misdemeanour matters and may or may not be punished, such behaviours are: nepotism, cronyism and political patronage.
- **Nepotism** – refers to the employment and/or promotion of close relatives in the state or public administration;
- **Cronyism** – refers to the employment and/or promotion of close friends in the state or public administration;
- **Political patronage** – refers to the employment and/or promotion of party members to high positions in the state or public administration. Clientelism and patronage are related to patronage and mean providing privileges to clients, favouring certain people for the sake of protection or a certain (most often party/political) merit;
- **White** – corruption encompasses those corrupt behaviours that in certain environments, due to the cultural matrix and value concepts, are not considered immoral, and therefore are not legally sanctioned. For example, giving items of small amount or value as a sign of gratitude for a successfully completed service (in an ambulance, hospital, at the counter, etc.) (Pecova Ilievska et al. 2020).

According to a study by the Institute for Communication Studies, a chart of the Most Burning Topics Related to Environmental Corruption has been prepared, from which the risks of environmental corruption are clearly mapped (FOSM, 2022):

Chart No. 1 - Most Burning Topics Related to Environmental Corruption:

Најгорливи теми поврзани со корупција во животната средина

According to this graph, at the very top are the construction mafia, air pollution from industrial complexes, illegal construction, and next to them are the misuse of mineral resources, illegal logging, construction in protected areas, and the opening of mines. Of course, the less risky categories of environmental corruption are also listed here, but no less significant, because this is a survey to which citizens responded.

Of course, in terms of divisions or forms of corruption, there are other types, but for the needs of the work, we believe that these are quite sufficient.

4.1 Corruption scenarios in environmental procedures

Recent assessments highlight several recurring corruption scenarios that undermine the integrity of environmental decision-making in North Macedonia. These scenarios reveal that corruption is not limited to individual wrongdoing but is embedded within procedural weaknesses, administrative discretion, and institutional fragmentation.

A common corruption scheme involves the manipulation of EIA reports, political interference in inspections, non-transparent public participation, and preferential treatment in permitting (Florozone, 2023a; 2023b).

5. PHENOMENOLOGY OF CORRUPTION IN THE ENVIRONMENT

Corruption in environmental governance involves employees, inspectors, judiciary, and politicians. Techniques include bribery, forgery, concealment of crimes, reassignment, and impunity through statutes of limitations. Examples include:

- **An employee forged permits for cutting wood – has charged 200 euros per truck** (Petrovska Rajović, 2024). An employee of PE Makedonski Shumi in Strumica issued forged wood-cutting permits for 12,000 denars per truckload to those transporting unstamped firewood, committing "abuse of official position", "forgery of an official document", and "embezzlement in office", causing a loss of 186,200 denars to the Subsidiary "Belasica".
- **Criminal case for an employee of "National Forests" forging an official document** (Makfax 2024). In July 2023, a clerk at PE National Forests, Karadžica – Skopje, falsified a delivery document, reporting 4 cubic meters of firewood while the truck carried a much larger amount.
- **Charges filed against the head of the Galičica Forestry Department and another person for felling an oak tree** (OHRIDPRES 2024). The Galičica Regional Forestry Department filed charges against an employee for "abuse of official position and authority" related to forest destruction (Art. 226 CC), causing damage of 1,434,510 denars.
- **Major action against wood thieves: Criminal charges for abuse of official position, obstruction of justice...**(2024). Criminal charges were filed against five individuals—three from Valandovo Forest Police and two from PE "National Forests" – Salandžak Valandovo—for "abuse of official position and authority" (Art. 353) and "obstruction of justice" (Art. 368-a). They had previously committed similar offences on three occasions without being detected.

Experts warn that pollution from industrial complexes can have severe consequences; accidents, especially on a large scale, pose a threat to land, rivers, lakes, groundwater, and human health, with flotation tailings ponds often referred to as "**flotation atomic bombs**" due to their potential environmental and health risks (Kostadinov et al., 2012). Perpetrators are often motivated by illegally acquired profits, while state representatives may be influenced by material or immaterial benefits, rights, privileges, or employment.

High-level corruption cases, such as the no-confidence vote of judges in the Republic Judicial Council and the president of the State Commission for the Prevention of Corruption, highlight systemic weaknesses in public office integrity, selection processes, and accountability. Although only the second case directly relates to environmental issues, both demonstrate how influence, impunity, and procedural delays allow corruption to persist, undermining public trust.

Networks of corruption involve coordinated activities affecting prosecution, judiciary, and public administration, often leading to impunity through legal loopholes, evidence gaps, reduced sentences, and statute of limitations. These examples illustrate that while many corrupt activities are known and sometimes investigated, the investigation and judicial processes are frequently compromised, resulting in cases ending without convictions.

The above-mentioned examples, and of course the 2020 SCPC Report supported by the OSCE, detect the weak points in the environment through which the "Rules of the Game" are circumvented:

- A broad legal framework and many sub-sectors that are differently aligned with European legislation, which leaves room to “turn a blind eye” to the full application of environmental standards;
- Insufficient implementation of the legislation;
- Impunity for corrupt behaviour, when the legislation is not applied at all;
- Different interpretations of the conditions and required documents;
- Delayed application of environmental measures for certain companies;
- Political influence and pressures from the private sector for delayed implementation of environmental permits and other environmental protection documents (Pushevski, 2024)

In addition to what has been presented by us about the causes and phenomenology of this phenomenon, we believe that there are still specific indicators that have not been discovered.

6. PREVENTION OF FUTURE CRIMINAL ACTIVITIES

Preventive mechanisms against corruption in environmental governance include trainings, workshops, media campaigns, short films, and highlighting prosecuted cases to demonstrate consequences. Strengthening public participation is essential: transparent access to Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) and Strategic Environmental Assessment (SEA) documents, environmental permits, and inspection reports allows citizens meaningful engagement. Public hearings should be inclusive and well-advertised, while civil society organizations can monitor, provide legal support, and participate in oversight (Floazon, 2023b).

Secure and confidential reporting channels—such as hotlines, online platforms, and whistleblower protections—enable reporting without fear of retaliation. Capacity-building for local authorities, inspectors, and civil society enhances understanding of roles and responsibilities, ensuring governance is transparent, accountable, and resilient. Preventive activities should also target education, local communities, border regions, and employees within environmental, police, judicial, and penal institutions. By combining these measures, the deterrence effect is strengthened, and opportunities for corruption and environmental harm are significantly reduced (Marjanović, 2003; Sajkova Zafirovska, 2024; Floazon, 2023b).

7. CONSEQUENCES OF THE IMPACTS OF CORRUPTION ON THE ENVIRONMENT

Despite preventive mechanisms, corruption continues to profoundly affect environmental governance. Public officials responsible for legal action in environmental cases are often influenced through personal or family ties to polluting entities. Polluters exert pressure via politicians, claiming that punishment would cause mass job losses and social instability, while making substantial financial contributions disguised as donations or sponsorships. This allows officials to accumulate wealth far beyond that of ordinary citizens, often laundered through domestic or international investments. Notably, after nearly 35 years of independence, the Law on the Origin of Acquired Property has still not been passed—and as things stand, it is unlikely to be enacted for the next 135 years.

All participants in the fight against corruption must approach their work with the utmost seriousness, ensuring that processes progress efficiently toward court verdicts. This does not imply haste or superficiality, nor should it involve omissions, mistakes, or illegal

actions that allow perpetrators to evade responsibility. Such failures only enable the continuation of similar criminal activities in the environmental sector.

Meanwhile, citizens bear the most direct consequences: landslides, floods causing material damage and loss of life, pollution of air, water, and soil, and contamination of food. These factors increase mortality, cause diseases in humans, plants, and animals, and contribute to rising rates of malignant and unexplained health problems, particularly in highly polluted areas such as Skopje, Veles, Bitola, Kavadarci, and Negotino. These impacts strain the country's health, social, economic, and financial systems. According to UNICEF's *Breathless Beginnings* report (2024), air pollution in North Macedonia claims approximately 5,000 lives annually, comparable to wartime casualties (Mirčevska Jovanović et al., 2024).

Persistent corruption undermines public trust in institutions and disproportionately affects marginalized communities, highlighting social inequities and environmental injustice (Florozon, 2023b). Presenting this stark picture of environmental degradation and corruption underscores the urgent need for officials to responsibly perform the duties for which they are compensated by citizens' taxes.

CONCLUSIONS

If the main goal of the paper is to sublimate the impacts of corruption on the environment and through it an attempt is made to bring these activities closer to the scientific and professional public, the student population and the youth, but at the same time to reach every citizen of the country and the non-governmental sector, then this goal has been achieved by preparing the paper. It is precisely this goal that has enabled us to present more publicly available and research data that directly and indirectly improve our picture of the phenomenon that, from a professional perspective, has unimaginable and invaluable consequences. On the other hand, we sincerely hope that this paper would be an occasion and reason for future larger, more comprehensive, more detailed and certainly longer-term multi-scientific research. If, at least a little, we have raised awareness among the people who are directly responsible for the care and prevention of criminal activities in the environment and especially on corruption in it, then our goal has been achieved. But at the same time, raising awareness among the scientific and research population through our actualization of this problem and raising it to a higher level. The third element is raising awareness among citizens and civil society organizations regarding corruption and its impact on the environment. In order for all of this to be achievable, the following is necessary. No conclusion can be complete, but still, preventing and eliminating this phenomenon of environmental corruption must start from the youngest age so that it can continue throughout life. Namely, it is necessary to actively include topics of environmental protection and protection from corrupt activities from preschool age and then in school age from primary and secondary education, which would be upgraded in higher education, where all curricula would include subjects of environmental protection and measures and activities against corrupt activities. On the other hand, it is necessary to strengthen the controls, supervision and capacities of the competent inspection bodies, develop standard operating procedures for dealing with immediate harmful consequences, their connection and harmonization of activities with other bodies, expeditiousness and cooperation with other competent bodies in the field, leaving no possibility of omission of their legal activities in order to protect anyone's personal interests because there would be responsibility for the same. At the same time, it is necessary to tighten the penal policy that

would reflect both on the perpetrators and on the competent investigative and judicial bodies, which in any way and with any action help and enable the perpetrators not to be punished or to receive some symbolic punishment. Perhaps the most important thing is to unite the non-governmental sector, increase its cooperation so that evidence that has not been collected by the state authorities, which are obliged to do so, can be provided in a timely, accurate and appropriate manner, and to mobilize the public in a timely manner, which, through appropriate pressure, will force the state authorities to implement their legal competencies for which they were formed and paid, while at the same time assuming an obligation under international ratified conventions to act appropriately and provide information.

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